

On-the-Job Training and Academic Performance of Business Administration Students Batch 2016-2017

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Abstract:- This study determined the level of student's academic performance Curriculum Degree Program like English/Language, Accounting, and Marketing along with the professional subjects. This also determined their on-the-job training (OJT) performances in relation to their attitudes and perception towards the job, their job performances, obedience to the policies of company and their working standards as assessed by their superiors. This serves as a tool to determine the attitudes and characteristics that graduating students must possess as they get employed after graduating. Their performance inside the school in terms of their Final Grades in both General and Professional Education courses served as reference with regards to their knowledge, understanding and performance during their college studies at the university. The analysis between their academic performances and their OJT performances indicate how well and how valuable the knowledge, theories and skills taught, developed, and inculcated while taking the course which are to be applied in their actual working environment.

Keywords:- Component; Internship, Skill, Competencies, On-the-Job Training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gaining knowledge is acquired through different aspects like home, school and other avenues. Constructive education is gained in school by studying various subjects with principles necessary for future employment. As students enter the tertiary education, they would encounter not just theory of what they studied but also to apply their knowledge to gain skills in the on- the- job training (OJT) program, where students are trained to absorb different kind of experiences on which it will nourish their minds in their chosen industry as well as their personal view and social commitments.

OJT plays a significant role in the curriculum of every degree program, which serves as a venue for the students to practice what they have learned from concepts and principles in developing work ethics, attitude and produce effective, efficient, and be globally competitive professionals. This hands-on experience aims to apply the knowledge, demonstrate necessary skills, enhancing the attitude and the character of the students towards a holistic appreciation of the actual workplace. This is where the students will be given job assignments that will test their ability to accomplish certain task. They are being observed and all their accomplishments are being evaluated based on the criteria set by the academic institution. This is where the student outcomes of the

Business Administration students can manifest through the application of basic and advanced knowledge in Accounting and English as well as the soft skills.

OJT is one of the mechanics of Higher Education industries in developing the needed competencies of its graduates. Within a specific number of hours, universities and colleges require their students to perform such training as part of the curriculum. Its goals and objectives served as a guide in developing the needed competencies for a particular job, and translating the training into a gainful working experience.

On-the-job training's objectives are to create opportunities for the students to learn about their chosen profession in a specific period of time. Along with this program are trainings that are provided by some companies from different industries in which the trainee gains knowledge as well as contributing to the organization. Through their supervision and support, trainees will nurture the knowledge that can build up their potentials on being professionals. Work values are also generated to the students through the experience given by this program that will really help them as they enter the business world. This program will provide students a concrete face to face with the real world of work.

The students' performance or academic achievement plays an important role in producing the best quality graduates who will become great leader and manpower for the country thus responsible for the country's economic and social development.

The effect of on the job training program on abilities and qualities advancement of the students rely on upon the methodologies of the gifted tutors or mentors to enhance the student learners' skill in the classroom and additionally the ideas that both the school and the trades cooperate in the preparation of mechanical students as future modern labourers. The school gave related aptitudes; the part of ventures is to work on the student's capabilities and exercises, accordingly, collaborating enterprises ought to give the students the vital stores expected to develop their execution level of capability and particular abilities and field of specialization.

The researchers wanted to clearly determine what subjects to improve and to level those subjects in the field of training. To give attention to the areas where the students need to enhance and focus on the performance. Different targets incorporate giving input, enhancing communication, understanding training needs, clearing up parts and duties. Distinguishes areas where coaching is fundamental and urges

teachers to play a dynamic instructing part. Action plan must be prepared to the students who will take business course. This research will provide various suggestions on what fields will it be best to take OJT that the university will recommend to the students at their final year.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study distinguishes the business administration students' academic performance and their internship performance appraisals from one academic program.

Specifically the study aimed to determine the level of OJT performance of BA students for the year 2016-2017; to present the academic performance in the general education courses (English/Language, Accounting and Marketing); to present the academic performance in professional courses in terms of Basic Marketing and Fundamentals of Business Management to test the significant relationship between the academic performance and OJT performance; and to propose a plan necessary for the improvement of the internship program.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

The researcher used the quantitative-descriptive method where quantitative strategies focus on numerical investigation of information assembled and evaluated the information and data on appraisal report and performance in their academic based on the students' last grades in general courses and professional courses from first year to fourth year.

B. Participants

The study included the performance appraisal reports of all 4th yr. BSBA students who were enrolled in their OJT during the academic year 2016-2017. One hundred (100%) of OJT appraisal reports were collected and analysed that was from the records of the College of Management and Business Technology

C. Instruments

The instruments used in the research were the OJT assessment form or training plan used by Internship as a part of assessing the performance of its trainees evaluated by the superior of the On-the-Job Trainees after their 540-hours of training. These instruments were provided by the Industrial Linkages and Coordinator Office with the College of Management and Business Technology OJT coordinator.

D. Procedure

The researcher secured the copy of the grading sheet and the compiled OJT assessment forms which were rated by the superiors of the BSBA students' interns.

E. Data Analysis

The following data were used in analysing the performance of the Business Administration students who have taken their OJT course. The complied data from the evaluation tool were interpreted using weighted mean and rank to determine the level of performance of OJT and academic performance of latest interns of business administration program. Correlation method was also used to get the significant relationship of OJT performance and academic performance of the Business Administration Students Batch 2016-2017. The given scale was used to interpret the result of the evaluation tool: 4.50 – 5.00 = Poor (P); 3.50 – 4.49 = Fair (F); 2.50 – 3.49 = Good (G); 1.50 – 2.49 = Very Good (VG); 1.00 – 1.49 = Excellent (E). The given scale was used to interpret the result of academic performance: 1.00 = Outstanding; 1.25 = Excellent; 1.50 = Superior; 1.75 = Very Good; 2.00 = Good; 2.25 = Satisfactory; 2.50 = Fairly Satisfactory; 2.75 = Fair; 3.00 = Passing

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWOK

The study ensuring a successful internship requires a marriage of student abilities with appropriate supervision. Finding appropriate host organizations for internships presents unique challenges. Securing organizational projects or assignments that can be completed within a relatively short time frame and that provide appropriate experiences for the student's level of training is critical. The internship should entail meaningful projects that will contribute to a true learning experience, not menial tasks (Shoenfelt, Kottke & Stone, 2012).

Academic performance is an important component of success of the students during their entire schooling. It provides data and information to describe the level of ability to understand, comprehend, apply, analysed, evaluate and synthesize things related or interrelated to their disciplines. Determining its correlation with the on-the-job performance would make it clear to the curriculum developers and program implementers as well as teachers on how they should deliver better services to enhance both performances. In trying to strengthen the quality assurance system in Philippine higher education, institutions of higher learning were mandated to upgrade higher education curricular offerings to international standards (Valdez, 2012). The curriculum was developed to integrate an in depth academics, laboratories and field internship programs that will ensure the efficiency and quality to meet worlds class standards (Mejia, Manzano & Menez, 2014).

The study will based to clearly determine what subjects to improve and to level those subjects in the field of training. Different targets incorporate giving input, enhancing communication, understanding training needs, clearing up parts and duties. Distinguishes areas where coaching is fundamental and urges teachers to play a dynamic instructing part This research will provide various suggestions on what fields will it be best to take OJT that the university will recommend to the students at their final year.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Dresses neatly and appropriately for office work.	1.40	E	1
2. Has a pleasing personality, is cheerful and good humored.	1.40	E	2
3. Possesses above average oral and written communication skills	1.50	VG	3
4. Projects self-confidence and enthusiasm.	1.60	VG	5
5. Demonstrations leadership potential.	1.50	VG	3.5
Composite Mean	1.48	VG	

Table 1: Performance of the Respondents on Personal Characteristics

Table 1 shows the ratings of the supervisors to the interns in terms of personal characteristics. The ability of the interns to dress neatly and appropriately for office work got a rating of 1.40 which means excellent. The intern’s ability to have a pleasing personality, cheerful and good humoured got the same rank with possessing above average oral and written communication skills which has rating of 1.50. The intern’s capacity to project self- confidence and enthusiasm got ratings of 1.60 which means very good. The intern’s ability to demonstrate leadership potential got a rating of 1.50 which means very good also.

The indicator that dresses neatly and appropriately for office work rank first because the company wants the interns to be properly acquired and practiced the sense of being professional. This is one of the requirements when you are in the job or work. However, the last in the rank is the indicator which is demonstrates leadership potential. The reasons for this are that they have insufficient knowledge or actual experience on the job so they are afraid to commit mistake and to notice their mistake by their supervisor. Another reason is that they are not prepared well to handle situation and people in the field where it is all about working actually.

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Shows marked interest and pride in his/her task and responsibilities.	1.40	E	2
2. Demonstrate procedures and assist others when necessary	1.00	E	1
3. Cooperates willingly and fits easily to the group	1.00	E	1.5
4. Takes initiative to show for fellow trainees employee and customers.	1.40	E	2.5
5. Recognizes the authority and seek assistance.	1.50	VG	
Composite Mean	1.26	E	

Table 2: Performance of the Respondents on Attitudes towards the Job

Table 2 shows in terms of the attitudes towards the job, the intern’s ability to demonstrate procedures and assist others when necessary and willingly and fits easily to the group which has a rating of 1.00. Second in rank is the intern’s marked interest and pride in his/ her tasks and responsibilities. This has a rating of 1.40 which is the same rank with initiative to show empathy, respect, and support for fellow trainees, employees and customers. The intern’s recognizes the authority and seek assistance got the rating of 1.50. The composite mean score is 1.26 which means excellent.

The business administration interns demonstrate and procedures and assist others when necessary to do good job because they were trained in the school by their professor to do tasks or works by assisting other for the quality of their work. They can cooperate and fits easily to the group because their professional instructors give them group activities. The BSBA trainees took initiative to recognizes authority and seek assistance they did it very good. They are good to be recognized authorities in work because they were taught by their parents as well as their professors to be good individual with the others and share it to others who need it.

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Present at work most of the time	1.60	VG	2
2. Comes at work on time	1.50	VG	1
3. Perform tasks in an accurate and timely manner	1.80	VG	4
4. Notify the company with any shift misses.	1.75	VG	3
Composite Mean	1.66	VG	

Table 3: Performance of the Respondents on Punctuality

Table 3 presents the performance of the business administration students in terms of punctuality. The ability to come at work on time got the rating of 1.50 which means very good. The second rank is the intern’s skill to present at work most of the time got the rating of 1.60 which means very good. Majority of the intern’s notify the company with any shift misses got an average of 1.75 which means very good.

The trainees were performs tasks in an accurate and timely manner got the average of 1.80 which means very good.

The BSBA interns came at on time and follow the rules and regulation of the company. The trainees were properly trained to follow rules and regulation of the university and if they committed mistake they were prone to punishment which made them not to do it again. They were also present

at work most of the time because they wanted to learn more of the production in the company and finish their OJT on time.

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Demonstrate uses tools to improve efficiency	1.60	VG	2.5
2. Show interpersonal communication ability	1.50	VG	1
3. Seeks opportunities to work on teams as a means to develop experience and knowledge	1.60	VG	2.5
4. Show carefully weighs the priority of things to be done	1.80	VG	5
5. Demonstrate quickly and effectively solves customers problems	1.75	VG	4
Composite Mean	1.65	VG	

Table 4: Performance of the Respondents on Specific Work Competencies

Table 4 displays the ratings of the supervisors to the interns in terms of work competencies. The intern's show the interpersonal communication abilities got 1.50 which means very good in this aspect. The on-the-job trainee's capacity to demonstrate uses of information or business tools to improve efficiency and seek opportunities to work on teams as a means to develop experiences and knowledge got the same average of 1.60 which means very good. The intern's ability to demonstrate quickly and effectively solves customers

problem got a rating of 1.75 which means very good and show carefully weighs the priority of things to be done got the fifth rank with a rating of 1.80 which means very good.

The BSBA trainees showed interpersonal communication abilities because they are exposed and learned from other people outside the school and know the important of communication in their field and the like.

Courses/Subject	GWA	Interpretation
English/Language	1.75	Very Good
Accounting	2.25	Satisfactory

Table 5: Performance of the Respondents on General Education

*GWA – General Weighted Average

As seen from the Table 5, the student performed very good in their Language/English courses which obtained a general weighted average of 1.75 and verbally interpreted as very good. However, the respondents' only performed satisfactory in Accounting.

The students have very good performance in language/English subjects because they must train student and develop English proficiency among them. While in accounting subjects performs only satisfactory because accounting is difficult to make each student work in analysing problems that can be used in actual.

Courses/Subject	GWA	Interpretation
Principle of Marketing	1.50	Superior
POM (Product Operation Management)	2.0	Good
Advertising and Sales promotion	1.75	Very Good

Table 6: Performance of the Respondents on Professional Courses

Based from the results in Table 6, the students performed superior in Principles of Marketing which has a computed general weighted average of 1.50. While for the Product Operation Management courses only performed good and advertising and sales promotion courses is very good with the general weighted average of 1.75.

The study shows significant relationship in general education courses and personal characteristics. In general education courses which include language/English subject and accounting subject, being good in language makes you more confident on what they are going to say. It is easy for them to communicate and to deal with others. They can be expressive individual that enables them to express their feelings or thoughts about the work or perceptions on the situation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers arrived with the following conclusions to improve the internship:

- Most of the respondents have not enough self-confidence in handling situation
- Most students are inactive in exploring innovative things
- Most of the students are distracted and still requires assistance, too many tasks to turn in which makes a students from best to just good enough quality work.
- Demonstrating capability to deal with people and do professional responsibilities, most students didn't develop self-confidence to deal and express what they want to with people.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Comprehension and evaluation for regular subjects must be reinforced by the General Education Instructors keeping in mind the end goal to apply this learning in logical innovative work of organizations through including the building graduates in logical research workshop or building up an examination venture that would animate their enthusiasm to take part in finding new actualities.

The OJT Manual must be revisited regularly to make necessary updates, improvements and changes to fit into the present needs and demands of the private industry partners or government agencies. The OJT Coordinator ought to make on-the-spot visitation and monitor the student-trainees and participating offices with respect to the execution of the work assignments of the learners.

It is recommended that the orientation may be given through the lead of workshops, training and seminars to set up the trainee and help them get required skills and to see better the demand of the real business industry before leaving the entryways of the college and before the real encounter the business.

For the future researchers, advance studies with respect to the topic might be made to enhance and upgrade the OJT program of the BSBA and the OJT program of College of Management and Business Technology in general.

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